

Base Adducts of Bis (Salicylaldehydato) Copper (II) and Zinc (II)

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SEVERAL base adducts of beta-diketones of zinc (II) and copper (II) have been reported¹⁻⁴ earlier. The complexes of *o*-hydroxy aryl carbonyl compounds closely resemble those of beta-diketones. Therefore, it was thought worthwhile to study the base adduct formation with salicylaldehydato complexes.

Metal chelates were prepared by reacting ethanolic solution of metal chlorides with salicylaldehyde in (1:2) ratio followed by dropwise addition of sodium acetate solution. The precipitated compounds were washed with ethanol, ether and dried *in vacuo*. Bis-(salicylaldehydato) zinc (II) was suspended in ethanol, base was added in (1:2) ratio and the mixture refluxed till a clear solution was obtained. Cu(II) chelate was refluxed with the base as the solvent. On keeping the clear solutions overnight crystalline compounds separated out.

Metal in the compounds was estimated by standard methods, Conductance was measured in *M*/1000 acetone solution using "Toshniwal's conductivity bridge". Infrared spectra were recorded on Nujol mulls using Unicam SP-200 Spectrophotometer and electronic spectra in *M*/100 (chloroform base mixture) solution with Unicam SP-500 Spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility measurement were made on solid specimens using Gouy method.

Results and Discussion

The complexes reported in the present investigation are of the composition $[ML_2 B_2]$ where 'M' is Cu (II) or Zn, (II), LH-Salicylaldehyde and 'B' is the nitrogen base. Zinc complexes are white crystalline solids whereas copper (II) complexes are blue or green needleshaped crystals. The compounds have low melting points and are fairly soluble in acetone in which medium the Λ_M values are very low (1-4 mhos) suggesting non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. Magnetic susceptibility measurements of copper (II) complexes, show them to be paramagnetic (1.8-1.9 B.M.). Most of the ligand absorption bands are shifted. $\nu(M-O)$ could not be recorded as it was beyond the range of instrument. $\nu(C=O)$ of salicylaldehyde is found to be in the range of 1620-1640 cm^{-1} in the base adducts. The characteristic band due to conjugated C=O group of salicylaldehyde is observed at about 1660 cm^{-1} which shifts to lower frequency in the metal chelates (1605 cm^{-1}) and again slightly shifts to higher frequency in base adducts. Hence, all the complexes reported in the present investigation are six coordinated.

Copper (II) complexes in chloroformbase mixture show one broad absorption band in the 675-700 nm region ($\epsilon=80-100$). It has been observed^{5,6} that greenish colours and absorptions in the vicinity of 700 nm are indicative of penta- or hexa-coordinated Cu(II). Recent studies⁷ on electronic spectra of Cu (II) indicate that the three transitions :

$2B_1 \rightarrow 2A_1$ (ν_1), $2B_1 \rightarrow 2B_2$ (ν_2), $2B_1 \rightarrow 2E$ (ν_3) are close in energy and often give rise to a single broad band envelope. So the present complexes probably have a distorted octahedral configuration. This is in conformity with some earlier observations⁸ by Graddon *et al.*

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, MELTING POINT, CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF CU(II) AND ZN(II) COMPLEXES

Compounds	M.P. (°C.)	Λ_M (mhos)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	%Metal Found Calcd.	
$[\text{Zn}(\text{Sal})_2(\text{I.Q.})_2]$	204	2.0	—	12.61	12.98
$[\text{Zn}(\text{Sal})_2(\text{Q})]$	215	3.5	—	12.72	12.98
$[\text{Zn}(\text{Sal})_2(\text{beta-Picoline})_2]$	171	2.4	—	12.82	13.19
$[\text{Cu}(\text{Sal})_2(\text{I.Q.})_2]$	160	1.8	1.82	11.28	10.95
$[\text{Cu}(\text{Sal})_2(\text{Q})_2]$	217	1.5	1.88	11.28	10.89
$[\text{Cu}(\text{Sal})_2(\text{beta-Picoline})_2]$	120*	1.2	1.85	12.92	12.64

* Denotes decomposition.

Sal=Salicylaldehyde, Q=Quinoline. I.Q.=Isoquinoline.

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Physico-Chemical Studies on the Complex Formation of Zirconium and Thorium with some Organic Acid. Part II

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IN this communication a number of new complexes of zirconium and thorium with anthranilic acid and its halo derivatives are reported. The present study was carried out in order to see the effect of halo substitution on the chelation ability of HA.

Halo anthranilic acids were prepared by standard methods. Complexes were obtained by direct addition of potassium salt solution of the ligands to the metal solution in various molar ratios. The preparation method was same as described in a previous communication. Table 1 contains representative data of analysis of HA complexes. Analysis of the complexes of other acids revealed identical compositions.